

Studies on the Appearance of Polarographic Maxima of Aromatic Nitrocompounds Under Various Experimental Conditions

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The appearance of polarographic maxima of some aromatic nitrocompounds has been investigated under different experimental conditions i.e., at different pH of B.R. buffer, different concentration of the supporting electrolyte and depolarizer and different heights of mercury column. It is found that all the compounds, except *ortho*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *ortho*-nitrobenzoic acid, yield sharp polarographic maxima of first kind and that the maxima are of negative polarity. It is observed that the height of the maxima is influenced by the change in experimental conditions.

As most aromatic nitrocompounds give maxima in their reduction waves¹, it would be worthwhile to study the occurrence and nature of these maxima. Literature reveals that studies on this field are rather sparse. Lal and Srivastava² studied the effect of various experimental conditions such as concentration of depolarizer, height of mercury column and large resistances in series with the cell, on the polarographic negative maximum of nitrobenzene at pH 7 using McIlvaine buffer. This paper deals with the occurrence and nature of the polarographic maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids. The effects of pH, concentration of supporting electrolyte, concentration of depolariser and the height of mercury column on these maxima have also been investigated.

Experimental

All depolarizers used were B.D.H products. *o*- and *m*-nitrotoluenes were redistilled while *p*-nitrotoluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids were recrystallized from ethanol before use. The other chemicals viz., NaNO₃, boric acid, phosphoric acid, acetic acid and sodium hydroxide were of B.D.H., A. R. grade. The concentration of each depolarizer (in 4% ethanolic solution) was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Desired concentrations of various constituents of B.R. buffer for a desired pH were added to the solution to be polarographed. NaNO₃ was used as a supporting electrolyte in each case. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL 02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. All measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured

against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: for *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols: $m = 3.12 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$; $t = 2.6 \text{ sec}$; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.5 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$; $h_{\text{corr}} = 62.4 \text{ cm}$ (in 0.05 M NaNO₃, open circuit); for *o*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *o*-nitrobenzoic acid: $m = 3.03 \text{ mg/sec}$; $t = 2.44 \text{ sec}$; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.43 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$, $h_{\text{corr}} = 63.7 \text{ cm}$ (in 0.1 M NaNO₃, open circuit); for *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids: $m = 3.02 \text{ mg/sec}$; $t = 2.98 \text{ sec}$; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.51 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$; $h_{\text{corr}} = 62.8 \text{ cm}$ (in 0.1 M NaNO₃, open circuit).

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH on the appearance of the maxima on the C-V curves of aromatic nitrocompounds:

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrotoluenes: Each depolarizer gives a sharp maximum on the rising portion

Fig. 1. C-V curves of *o*-nitrotoluene at different pH of B.R. buffer. Plots 1-10 correspond to pH 1.98, 3.27, 4.10, 5.02, 6.09, 7.00, 7.95, 8.95, 10.10 and 11.20.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE AND DEPOLARIZER ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC MAXIMA OF *o*-, *m*- and *p*-NITROTOLUENES, NITROPHENOLS, NITROBENZALDEHYDES AND NITROBENZOIC ACIDS

Concentration <i>M</i>	<i>ortho</i> isomer		<i>meta</i> isomer		<i>para</i> isomer	
	<i>i</i> _{max} μA	- <i>E</i> _{max} V SCE	<i>i</i> _{max} μA	- <i>E</i> _{max} V SCE	<i>i</i> _{max} μA	- <i>E</i> _{max} V SCE
(i) Effect of concentration of supporting electrolyte (NaNO ₃)						
Nitrotoluenes						
[Depolarizer] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ ; h _{corr} = 62.4 cm ; pH = 7.0 (constant)						
[NaNO ₃]						
0.00	46.36	0.70	53.20	0.68	57.00	0.67
0.05	49.02	0.72	56.62	0.71	63.84	0.70
0.10	50.16	0.73	58.26	0.72	66.50	0.72
0.20	47.88	0.71	56.24	0.70	63.08	0.70
1.00	41.80	0.68	47.88	0.66	50.92	0.65
Nitrophenols						
[Depolarizer] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ ; h _{corr} = 62.4 cm ; pH = 6.09 (constant)						
0.00	80.56	0.56	60.55	0.60	83.60	0.60
0.05	88.16	0.58	61.60	0.61	95.88	0.65
0.10	74.48	0.54	59.50	0.60	79.80	0.62
0.20	66.88	0.53	54.60	0.58	74.48	0.60
0.50	55.48	0.51	47.60	0.55	68.40	0.57
1.00	40.28	0.48	43.05	0.50	54.72	0.53
Nitrobenzaldehydes						
[Depolarizer] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ ; h _{corr} = 63.7 cm ; pH = 7.0 (constant)						
0.00	No max	—	45.60	0.64	28.70	0.52
0.02	"	—	49.40	0.65	29.40	0.53
0.05	"	—	49.02	0.65	28.00	0.52
0.10	"	—	44.08	0.64	26.60	0.51
0.50	"	—	38.00	0.60	21.00	0.50
1.00	"	—	31.16	0.58	18.20	0.48
Nitrobenzoic acids						
[Depolarizer] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ ; h _{corr} = 62.8 cm ; pH = 5.02 (constant)						
0.00	No max	—	76.80	0.54	61.44	0.53
0.04	"	—	82.56	0.56	67.20	0.55
0.05	"	—	84.48	0.56	70.40	0.56
0.10	"	—	87.68	0.57	71.68	0.56
0.50	"	—	73.60	0.54	65.28	0.54
1.00	"	—	64.00	0.52	57.60	0.52
(ii) Effect of concentration of depolarizer						
Nitrotoluenes						
[NaNO ₃] = 0.10 <i>M</i> ; h _{corr} = 62.4 cm ; pH = 7.0 (constant)						
[Depolarizer]						
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	No max	—	No max	—	No max	—
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	19.00	0.69	27.36	0.68	30.40	0.69
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	50.16	0.73	58.26	0.72	66.50	0.72
1.5 × 10 ⁻³	72.20	0.75	89.30	0.75	101.84	0.74
2.0 × 10 ⁻³	102.60	0.77	120.08	0.77	136.80	0.78
2.5 × 10 ⁻³	129.20	0.80	150.10	0.79	171.00	0.80
Nitrophenols						
[NaNO ₃] = 0.05 <i>M</i> ; h _{corr} = 62.4 cm ; pH = 6.09 (constant)						
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	No max	—	No max	—	No max	—
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	39.52	0.54	30.10	0.58	38.76	0.61
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	88.16	0.58	61.60	0.61	85.88	0.65
1.5 × 10 ⁻³	138.32	0.60	94.15	0.63	133.38	0.67
2.0 × 10 ⁻³	182.40	0.62	125.65	0.65	177.84	0.70
2.5 × 10 ⁻³	229.52	0.65	157.15	0.70	224.30	0.74
Nitrobenzaldehydes						
[NaNO ₃] = 0.02 <i>M</i> ; h _{corr} = 63.7 cm ; pH = 7.0 (constant)						
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	No max	—	No max	—	No max	—
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	"	—	21.00	0.60	14.00	0.49
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	"	—	49.40	0.65	29.40	0.53
1.5 × 10 ⁻³	"	—	68.25	0.67	45.50	0.55
2.0 × 10 ⁻³	"	—	102.60	0.69	63.00	0.58
2.5 × 10 ⁻³	"	—	133.60	0.72	87.50	0.60

Nitrobenzoic acids

[NaNO₂] = 0.10 M ; h_{corr} = 62.8 cm ; pH = 5.02 (constant)

2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	No max	-	No max	-	No max	-
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	"	-	41.60	0.53	32.00	0.52
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	"	-	87.68	0.57	71.68	0.56
1.5 × 10 ⁻³	"	-	134.40	0.59	112.00	0.58
2.0 × 10 ⁻³	"	-	185.60	0.61	150.40	0.60
2.5 × 10 ⁻³	"	-	230.40	0.64	192.00	0.63

of the C-V curves in the pH range 1.98-10.10 (representative Fig. 1). At pH > 10.10, however, no maximum appears. The height of the maximum in respect of each depolarizer is influenced by pH in the range 1.98-10.10. In the case of *o*-nitrotoluene the height of maximum (*i*_{max}) sharply decreases in the pH range 1.98-3.27, but with a further increase in pH it tends to increase and reaches a maximum at pH 7 and thereafter in the pH range 7.95-10.10 it gradually decreases. In the case of *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes the height of the maximum gradually decreases in the pH range 1.98-4.10 and thereafter it tends to increase gradually and reaches a maximum at pH 7. Beyond this, a decrease is observed.

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrophenols : *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols give sharp maxima on the rising portion of the C-V curves in the pH range 1.98-6.09 (representative Fig. 2). However, at pH ≥ 7.00 no maximum appears in the case of *p*-nitrophenol. In the case of *o*- and *m*-nitrophenols this situation is

Fig. 2. C-V curves of *o*-nitrophenol at different pH of B.R. buffer. Plots 1-10 correspond to pH 1.98, 3.27, 4.10, 5.02, 6.09, 7.00, 7.95, 8.95, 10.10 and 11.20.

obtained at pH ≥ 7.95. The height of the maximum of each depolarizer is influenced by the pH in the range 1.98-7.00. In the case of *o*-nitrophenol the height of maximum (*i*_{max}) is greatest at pH 1.98, but with a further increase in pH it tends to decrease and reaches minimum at pH 5.02. At pH 6.09 it

sharply increases and thereafter at pH 7 it sharply decreases. Beyond this pH no maximum appears on the C-V curves of *o*-nitrophenol. In the case of *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols the height of maximum gradually increases as pH increases from 1.98 to 6.09. Beyond this range (at pH 7), there occurs a sharp fall in the height of the maximum of *o*- and *m*-nitrophenols but no maximum appears in the case of *p*-nitrophenol.

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrobenzaldehyde : It is observed that *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde does not yield a maximum on the C-V curves in the entire pH range (1.98-11.98) but *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes yield sharp maxima (representative Fig. 3) on the rising

Fig. 3. C-V curves of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde at different pH of B.R. buffer. Plots 1-9 correspond to pH 1.98, 3.27, 4.10, 5.02, 6.09, 7.00, 7.95, 8.95 and 10.10.

portion of the C-V curves in the pH range 3.27-8.95 and 6.09-11.98, respectively. In the case of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde no maximum appears on the C-V curves at pH > 8.95 while in the case of *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde this happens at pH < 6.09. At lower pH (1.98) none of the two isomers (*m*- and *p*-) gives a maximum on the C-V curves. In the case of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde the height of the maximum gradually increases as the pH increases from 3.27 to 7.0, and reaches a maximum at pH 7.0. Thereafter it sharply decreases in the pH range 7.95-8.95. In the case of *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde the height of the maximum tends to increase as pH increases from 6.09 to 7.0. Beyond pH 7.0, a gradual decrease is observed.

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrobenzoic acids : Whereas *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid give sharp maxima (representative Fig. 4) on the rising portion of the C-V curves in the pH range 1.93-7.00 and 1.98-7.95 respectively, *o*-nitrobenzoic acid does not yield a maximum on the C-V curves in the entire pH range of 1.98-11.98. In the case of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid no maximum appears on the C-V curves at pH > 7.00 while the same is true for *p*-nitrobenzoic acid at pH > 7.95. In the case of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid the height of the maximum increases gradually as the pH increases from 1.98 to 4.10 and then increases sharply to a maximum at pH 5.02. Thereafter (at pH > 5.02) it decreases gradually in the beginning and then sharply as the pH increases from 5.02 to 7.0. In the case of *p*-nitrobenzoic acid the height of the maximum tends to increase gradually as the pH increases from 1.93-5.02 but a sharp fall occurs from pH 6.09 to 7.95.

Fig. 4. C-V curves of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid at different pH of B.R. buffer. Plots 1-11 correspond to pH 1.98, 3.27, 4.10, 5.02, 6.09, 7.00, 7.95, 8.95, 10.10, 11.20 and 11.98.

The values of i_{max} and E_{max} for all the depolarizers have been determined and it has been found that at pH 7.0, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes, at pH 6.09, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols and at pH 5.02, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids yield well-defined and sharp maxima. Therefore, these pH values have been selected for studying the effect of various experimental conditions on the maxima of these depolarizers.

Nature and polarity of the maxima : Since the maxima of *ortho*, *meta* and *para* isomers of nitrotoluene and nitrophenol and of *meta* and *para* isomers of nitrobenzaldehyde and nitrobenzoic acid appear on the rising portion of the C-V curves, these are therefore of first kind. The maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes and nitrophenols; *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and nitrobenzoic acids lie at $-0.73V$, $-0.72V$ and $-0.72V$; $-0.58V$, $-0.61V$ and $-0.65V$; $-0.65V$ and $-0.53V$; and

$-0.57V$ and $-0.56V$ (vs SCE), respectively from the potential of the electrocapillary zero, which is $-0.36V$, $-0.32V$, $-0.36V$, and $-0.30V$ (vs SCE), respectively under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ values of all the depolarizers also lie on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero the maxima of these depolarizers are of negative polarity⁴.

Effect of concentration of supporting electrolyte on the maxima : The effect of increasing concentrations of $NaNO_3$ on the maxima of these depolarizers (concentration of the depolarizer and all other experimental conditions remaining the same) has been studied and the values of i_{max} and E_{max} have been listed in Table 1. The table shows that the value of i_{max} for *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes and *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids increases as the concentration of $NaNO_3$ increases from 0.0 to 0.10 *M*; while that for *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols, it increases as the concentration of $NaNO_3$ is increased from 0.0 to 0.05 *M*. The same is true for *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes for an increase in the concentration of $NaNO_3$ upto 0.02 *M*.

Effect of the concentration of the depolarizer on the maxima : The effect of the concentration of the depolarizer (keeping all other experimental conditions constant) on the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids has been investigated and the values of i_{max} and E_{max} for different concentrations of the depolarizers have been listed in Table 1. It has been found that at lower concentration ($2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$) of the depolarizer, no maximum appears while at $5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ a small maximum appears on the C-V curves of these depolarizers. This implies that there is an optimum concentration of the depolarizers at which the maximum would appear. With further increase in the concentration ($>5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$) of each depolarizer the height of the maximum (i_{max}) increases and E_{max} gets shifted to more negative potentials.

Effect of the height of mercury column on the maxima : Keeping the concentration of the depolarizer and of supporting electrolyte and all other

Fig. 5. C-V curves of *o*-nitrotoluene at different height of the mercury column. 1-62.4 cm; 2-52.4 cm; 3-42.4 cm; 4-32.4 cm.

experimental conditions constant, the influence of the height of mercury column on the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrotoluenes, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids was investigated. It has been observed that a decrease in i_{max} and a positive shift in E_{max} occurs as the height of the mercury column decreases (representative Fig. 5.)

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